

THE MAIN CONDITIONS FOR IMPROVING THE MARKETING STRATEGY AT "MAROKAND-PARRANDA" LLC JV

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Abstract. *In this article, poultry enterprises study the stages of development of marketing strategies, expansion of product types and quality improvement; introduction of scientific organization of work; product processing is considered.*

Keywords: *enterprise, production, strategy, product, competition, customer, poultry, concentration.*

ОСНОВНЫЕ УСЛОВИЯ СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЯ МАРКЕТИНГОВОЙ СТРАТЕГИИ СП ООО «МАРОКАНД-ПАРАНДА»

Аннотация. *В данной статье птицеводческие предприятия изучают этапы разработки маркетинговой стратегии, расширения видов продукции и улучшения качества; внедрение научной организации труда; считается переработка продукта.*

Ключевые слова: *предприятие, производство, стратегия, продукт, конкуренция, заказчик, птицеводство, соконцентрация.*

INTRODUCTION

In the republic, strategic thinking is becoming one of the important tools of socio-economic reforms. In the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, it is noted that "timely and effective implementation of the action strategy is the most important and main priority for all state authorities and their officials."

The foreign experience of marketing activities based on market development patterns and encouraging the effective work of enterprise divisions is a valuable school of rational management in the transition period and even more developed market.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

RESULTS

The purpose of our scientific research on the market of poultry products is to suggest ways to develop marketing activities and strategies of trading enterprises.

In order to achieve this goal, the following tasks were defined and performed in the article:

Definition of marketing strategy and its place in marketing theory; Study of different strategies as well as stages of development of marketing strategies.

Studying methods of strategic analysis of external and internal organization;

Study of the current state of marketing strategy of "Marokand-Parranda" LLC.

Study of the main competitors of "Marokand-Parranda" LLC;

In developing marketing strategies "Marokand - Parranda" JV should take into account the possibility of internal growth in external growth. Internal growth means the strategy of increasing the internal potential of the enterprise. External growth refers to the strategy of creating additional capacity by attracting additional investments.

"Marokand-Parranda" JV LLC can basically follow four internal strategies:

- Deeper Market Penetration Concentration: This requires a company to focus on doing better what it is already doing well. For example, further development of egg production technology;

- Market development: In this case, the company provides products with possible modifications to buyers in the relevant markets, that is, the search for other market segments.

- Product Development: Making significant changes or additions to existing products to increase market penetration among existing customer groups.

- Update: Relates to significant changes to a product or service. It involves the replacement of existing products with new ones, which means the life cycle of a new product.

External growth strategies are often implemented through acquisitions, mergers, vertical integration, and diversification. The following are particularly common:

- Horizontal integration: occurs when a company acquires or merges with a major competitor or a company operating in the same stage of the value chain.

- Vertical integration: Usually involves the acquisition of a company that supplies the firm with raw materials or is a buyer of its products and services. This can be done in reverse (ie controlling the supply of raw materials) or forward (eg controlling the distribution network).

- Concentric diversification: involves introducing products or services into areas related to existing products or services through technology or marketing. There is a possibility of synergy, i.e. when the total result exceeds the sum of the individual results of two activities.

- Conglomerate diversification: involves entering into areas of goods or services not directly related to existing technologies or markets. This is a high risk strategy.

- Functional cost analysis is one of the most effective methods of cost reduction widely used in the industry of different countries. This method makes it possible to improve the design of products, ensures their competitiveness in the foreign market, helps to reduce the cost of products, and optimize the processes of production organization and management. With the competent application of functional cost analysis, it is possible to reduce costs by up to 30%, dramatically increase product and production profitability, improve the quality characteristics of products, and increase all financial results.

- It is necessary to check the ability of the enterprise to carry out extended reproduction and social development at the expense of its own funds, that is, to determine its self-financing capabilities, taking into account the identified reserves for profit growth. The ability to self-finance is determined by the ratio of the need for investments for industrial and social development and the real financial opportunities to meet the existing need.

It is necessary to take measures to increase the volume of sales by mastering new trade markets, increasing the production of highly profitable products, reducing the cost of products due to the economical use of material, labor and other production resources, and increasing the productivity of employees due to the reduction of downtime. introducing new modern equipment that reduces the labor intensity of the production process, increasing the share of equity capital, returning the invested funds on time.

In the process of research, we identified and revealed the socio-economic, organizational and technical characteristics of strategy development.LLC "Marokand - Parranda" JV, according to the specific characteristics and level of development of the network, including:

uniform production and full use of labor resources throughout the year;
independence from weather conditions;
production under controlled microclimatic factors;
purchase of a flock of poultry uniformly throughout the year;
high level of production automation and mechanization;
feeding the birds purchased feed;
use of biological means of labor;
harmony of the natural process of production with the economic one;
less reliance on quantity and quality husbandland;
stability demand as the first necessary product;
flexibility in changing the scale of production compared to other industries animal husbandry;
completed technological process; specializes in the production of finished products.

When building a strategy for the development of a poultry enterprise, the following principles should be followed: consistency and continuity of forecasting and planning; taking into account the natural and economic conditions of production; unity of the process of stabilization and sustainable development of poultry enterprises; Social responsibility is not only the responsibility for creating working conditions for the company's employees and improving its efficiency, but also for the region and the entire society as a responsibility for creating conditions for training and retraining employees and increasing the level of personnel qualification; focusing on the production of a wide range of products based on the economic interests of the region, taking into account the balance, economic trends in the country and the world; development principle,

In addition, it is appropriate to develop the stages of the process of establishing a strategy for the development of poultry enterprises in the egg and meat-growing areas of Samarkand region, which includes alternative development strategies: production intensification strategy, innovative strategy, energy and resource saving strategy, extended reproduction strategy, marketing strategy and others.

The analysis of optimal options showed that "Marokand-Parranda" LLC has the possibility to increase the production of eggs (the main type of product) to 48.9 million units. and poultry meat (by-product) up to 102 tons per year under the optimistic development scenario. At the same time, the average annual livestock of all sexes and age groups is 154,000 heads, and the volume of sales of poultry products is increasing.

In addition, chicken egg processing products are characterized by a wide demand for it, the market is more competitive, and the demand for whole eggs is seasonal, since poultry farms are forced to reduce the price of their products in the summer. , an egg processing business project was developed at Marokand-Parranda LLC.

As a result of the calculations, the feasibility and profitability of the business project on the introduction of equipment and chicken egg processing shop at the poultry farm of "Marokand-Parranda" LLC was determined.

Proposals on organizational and economic measures to achieve strategic high rates of expanded reproduction in poultry enterprises, including: acceleration of scientific and technical development; the use of high-yielding poultry crosses; feeding poultry with complete feed;

application of effective veterinary preventive measures; appenergy- and resource-saving technologies; expanding product types and improving quality; introduction of scientific organization of work; deepening the processing of products, etc.

Strategic development of organizations is an important activity of modern production enterprises. In our final qualification work, the task of conducting theoretical and practical research on the organization of marketing strategy was set. As a result of research, we came to the following conclusions.

Marketing strategy is a set of measures aimed at forming long-term competitiveness of the enterprise. Strategy takes advantage of the development of the enterprise in a changing environment.

In strategic marketing, a strategy development procedure has been developed, which includes the development of a mission, strategic goals, analysis of the external environment, strategy development and its implementation.

DISCUSSION

"Marokand - Bird" LLC JV is one of the leading enterprises in the region for egg production. Its capacity is 50 million eggs per year. More than 47 million eggs were produced and sold at the enterprise in 2016. As a result, financial indicators improved, and the company's market position was strengthened.

Strategic analyzes showed that the main competitors are two enterprises - "Samarkand-Parranda" LLC and "Lohmann-Parranda" LLC JV. Four more businesses are currently joining, so competition is intensifying.

The main strategy of JV "Marokand-Parranda" LLC is to reduce the cost of egg production and improve distribution channels. In general, the company uses a strategy of concentration on egg production.

CONCLUSIONS

As a result of theoretical and practical research, we developed proposals for improving the marketing strategy of JV "Marokand-Parranda" LLC, which are as follows.

1. Analysis of the effectiveness of the current strategy, taking into account the changes in the egg and chicken meat market.

2. It is necessary to implement a diversification strategy, that is, to organize another production, for example, to process eggs.

3. In order to increase the stability of the enterprise, a detailed analysis of foreign markets is necessary.

4. It is necessary to develop a marketing plan for the next three years.

5. In addition, we offer to develop a strategy for the promotion of goods in the markets of other regions.

The implementation of these activities and proposals will allow to develop a strategic marketing plan and increase the effectiveness of marketing activities at "Marokand-Parranda" LLC.

REFERENCES

1. Sh.M. Mirziyoev "New Development Strategy of Uzbekistan" completed second edition, Tashkent "Uzbekistan" publishing house, 2022, 416 p.
2. Sh.M. Mirziyoev "Humanity, goodness and creativity are the foundations of our national idea" Tashkent "TASVIR" publishing house, 2021 y 36 p.
3. The first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.A. Karimov "Our main task is to further increase the development of our country and the prosperity of our people" Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2010. 18 p.
4. Abduganiev A., Tolametova Z. Labor capacity of Uzbekistan. T.: "Labor", 1998. 96 p.
5. Under the editorship of K.K. Abdurakhmonov. - T.: Human development. Textbook. i.f.d., prof. "Science and technology", 2013.
6. Derevyagina L.N., Ivashkova N.I. Opit training marketing specialists in the system of additional professional education // Vestnik. 2001
7. Nasirov P. Abdullayeva L. Marketing is the basis of market economy. T.: "Teacher" 2008.
8. Bekmurodov A.Sh., Kosimova M.S., Safarov B.J., Marketing management: Study guide. - T.: TDIU, 2007. - 268 p.
9. Begmatov Sh. A. Kakhorov A.J. Scientific and methodological problems of introducing innovative marketing, "Economics and Education" magazine No. 5, September-October, 2016.
10. Musayeva Sh.A. Usmonova D.I. Innovative marketing: Study guide. - "TURON PUBLISHING" Samarkand 2021.
11. Azimovna M. S., Shokhrukhovich U. F., Sodirovich U. B. Problems in the Implementation of Quality Management Systems in Small Business Enterprises //Eurasian Research Bulletin. – 2022. – T. 7. – C. 54-57.
12. Azimovna M. S., Ilkhomovna U. D. Problems of Marketing in the System of Higher Education //Academic Journal of Digital Economics and Stability. – 2022. – T. 13. – C. 71-75.
13. Azimovna M. S., Ilkhomovna U. D., Shokhrukhovich U. F. INNOVATIVE STRATEGIES OF TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN //EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 1. – C. 1-4.
14. Musayeva S. A., Usmonova D. I., Usmanov F. S. Problems with Marketing Research in the Furniture Market //Eurasian Journal of Academic Research. – 2021.
15. Azimovna M. S., Shokhrukhovich U. F. Development Prospects of Business Subjects in the Republic of Uzbekistan //Web of Scholars: Multidimensional Research Journal. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 4. – C. 13-19.
16. Azimovna M. S., Ilkhomovna U. D., Shokhrukhovich U. F. The Concept of Marketing Policy in Trade and Service Enterprises //CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATIONS ON TOURISM MANAGEMENT AND FINANCE. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 8. – C. 1-5. SCIENCE AND INNOVATION INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL VOLUME 1 ISSUE 5 UIF-2022: 8.2 | ISSN: 2181-3337 105

17. Azimovna M. S., Shokhrukhovich U. F. Ways to expand network marketing and e-commerce in the wholesale of medicines //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876. – 2022. – T. 16. – №. 06. – C. 113-116.
18. Azimovna M. S., Abdurozиковich M. Z. Features of the pharmaceutical market of the Republic of Uzbekistan //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429. – 2022. – T. 11. – №. 06. – C. 201-206.
19. Azimovna M. S., Shohruxhovich U. S. THE ROLE OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS IN THE FOREIGN TRADE TURNOVER OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 6. – C. 110-112.
20. Azimovna M. S. IMPROVING THE STUDY OF CONSUMER BEHAVIOR //Gospodarka i Innowacje. – 2022. – C. 109-112.
21. Azimovna M. S. et al. Analysis of the main economic and marketing indicators of FE" DAKA-TEX" LLC //ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603. – 2022. – T. 11. – №. 06. – C. 4-7.
22. Azimovna M. S., Ilkhomovna U. D. Optimal principles of assessing the quality of graduates in higher education //Eurasian Scientific Herald. – 2022. – T. 8. – C. 233-238.
23. Azimovna M. S. THE MAIN DIRECTIONS OF THE MARKETING COMPLEX TO INCREASE THE EXPORT POTENTIAL OF PRODUCTS //FORMATION OF PSYCHOLOGY AND PEDAGOGY AS INTERDISCIPLINARY SCIENCES. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 9. – C. 20-23.
24. Azimovna M. S., Ilkhomovna U. D., Shokhrukhovich U. F. WAYS TO USE MARKETING INFORMATION IN THE PROCESS OF EVALUATING THE ENTERPRISE //World Economics and Finance Bulletin. – 2022. – T. 10. – C. 9-12.
25. Azimovna M. S., Shokhrukhovich U. F., Sodirovich U. B. ANALYSIS OF THE MARKET OF TOURIST PRODUCTS OF THE SAMARKAND REGION //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 4. – C. 422-427.
26. Azimovna M. S., Shokhrukhovich U. F., Rofejon o'g'li R. S. THE PROCEDURE FOR ORGANIZING MARKETING RESEARCH AT INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES IN THE CONTEXT OF MODERNIZATION IN UZBEKISTAN //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – C. 392-399.
27. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 No. PF-4947 "On the Strategy of Actions for Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan".